

(II). The optical purity was much higher in alkylarycarbinols than in alkylmethylecarbinols, which is hard to explain by steric factor alone, but is in agreement with a previous observation of Mosher *et al.* The method is very simple and may be useful for the preparation of partially active alcohols of known configuration.

TABLE

Alcohol ^a	Rotation observed ^b [α] _D ²⁵ in degree	Maximum lit. rotation	Optical purity ^c %	Configuration
EtCHOHMe	-0.132, - 0.365	13.87 ^d	0.95 - 2.8	R
Bu ^t CHOHMe	-1.02, - 1.19	20.85 ^d	4.9 - 5.7	R
Pr ⁱ CHOHMe	-0.62, - 0.875	5.34 ^d	11.6 - 16.4	R
Bu ^s CHOHMe	-0.93, - 1.40	7.71 ^d	12.1 - 18.2	R
PhCHOHMe	-1 8.52, +11.04	43.5 ^e	19.5 - 25.4	R
PhCHOHEt	+10.0, +10.82	28.7 ^e	34.8 - 37.7	R
PhCHOHBu ^t	+11.0, +16.25	24.4 ^e	45.0 - 66.6	R
PhCHOHP ^r	+16.2, +17.2	24.6 ^e	65.8 - 69.9	R
PhCH ₂ CHOHMe	0.0, 0.0	26.6 ^f	0.0, 0.0	R

(a) Rotation was taken in neat liquid. (b) Duplicate data are results of two different experiments. (c) Calculated as $100 \times [\alpha]_{\text{observed}} / [\alpha]_{\text{maximum}}$. (d) Ref. 5. (e) Ref. 6. (f) Ref. 7.

p-Methoxyacetophenone and β -necetonaphthone were not reduced at all by this reagent either in ether or in tetrahydrofuran. The reduction of benzyl methyl ketone yielded completely inactive alcohol. The failure in these cases is not clearly understood at present. Reduction of a few keto-esters and some other ketonic systems is under progress.

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